

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)
ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

**COUNSELLING AGAINST NEGLIGENCE OF EDUCATION OF THE GIRL CHILD IN DELTA
STATE OF NIGERIA**

OGHOUNU, A. E.

Department of Guidance and Counselling, Delta State University, Abraka.

Corresponding Author: aeoghounu@delsu.edu.ng, 08023328505

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10414590>

Abstract

The study examined the negligent attitude of parents regarding education of the girl child in Delta State. The study adopted the descriptive survey design in which a questionnaire titled Parental Attitude to Girl Child Education Scale (PAGES) was used to gather data from parents. Psychometric properties of the instrument were established. Face validity was established for the instrument by lecturers in the Department of Guidance and Counselling in Delta State University Abraka, while the reliability was determined using the Cronbach alpha which yielded r value of 0.79. A sample of 180 parents randomly drawn from the eight Local Government Areas in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State was used. Data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and t -test. Four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. All four hypotheses were accepted. It was found that disparity in educational and socio-economic background, gender and location of parents have no influence on the education of the girl child and that of parents in Delta State. The study recommended amongst others that campaigns should be intensified to create awareness to the door steps of every parent in Delta State and indeed in Nigeria regarding the importance of educating the girl child and the value of the girl child and the value of the girl child in self-development and contribution to family and national growth.

Keywords: Counselling, Negligence, Girl Child, Education

Introduction

In recognition of the importance of education in the development of the individual and the nation, the federal government of Nigeria in formulating the policy of education for the nation made education compulsory for every Nigerian child and indeed free at some levels or tiers of education (National Policy on Education, 2014). The U.N Charter in realizing the role education plays in the development of an individual, nations and the world generally also declared that education is a right of every child irrespective of age, religion, gender, and nationality or ethnic group. (Universal Declaration of Human Right, 1948, World Conference on Education, 1990, UNICEF 1990). Sadly, while the rate of illiteracy reducing around the world, underdeveloped and developing countries still lag behind (Buchholz, 2022). It is disheartening that in most parts of the world especially in African and other developing countries, the right to child education has largely been ignored by the primary agent of socialization which is called the family and in fact parents.

In Nigeria, this right to education has been denied the child on grounds of gender. (Michael, 2011). Perhaps, the most denied and neglected of this fundamental right to education is the girl child (Nigerian Girls Education Initiatives). It is pertinent to note that it is the professional responsibility of parents to raise their children, educate them and see them through

school and career development. It is one onerous responsibility of parents to give education to their children so as to grow to become independent, responsible, skilful, knowledgeable and be able to contribute to their living, survival and national development. It can therefore amount to irresponsibility and professional negligence of the role of parents to their children when parents fail to send their children to school for formal and modern education, which can make children become literate, acquire knowledge and skills necessary for survival and development of self, family and the nation at large. Negligence in fact, amounts to family malpractice.

Since government has provided for free and compulsory education especially for all children of school age in the National Policy on Education and the Universal Basic Education Programme in Nigeria, it behoves parents to ensure that their children are made available and avail them the opportunity to attend school and be educated. The Delta State government for instance has tried to enforce this go to school phenomenon by introducing Education Marshals to monitor the school going behaviour among school age children and their parents. The assumption is that it is the it is the responsibility of parents to make their children available, which responsibility parent have often neglected. This negligence on part of parents can be as a result of their background such as their gender, socio-economic, literacy and location. (Ada, 2007).

Statement of the Problem

The problem of the study is to know the extent that the background of parents along these dimensions have contributed to the negligence of the education of the girl child in Nigeria and especially in the Delta Sate. The girl child has been the most neglected by parents especially in the acquisition of education. Traditionally, most parents have reasoned that it is mere waste of time and resources to send their girl child to school for formal education. to most parents, the child will eventually end up in an husband's house and will not be breadwinner to the biological but to the newly acquired family. To some, their income is to low and so should not be spend or wasted on the education for the girl child. Again, the experience of parents is limited to their location. Those in the rural areas believes so much in taboos regarding, sex typing and sex-roles compared to those in the urban areas. Educated parents are likely to have their own attitude about educating the girl child compare to those parents who are not educated (Bukar 2011). This study was intended to investigate the contributions of these parental backgrounds to the negligence of the girl child education in Delta State to guide in the counselling against negligence of the girl child education.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of female and male parents in the negligence of the education of the girl child.
- HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of educated and non-education parents in the negligence of the education of the girl child.
- HO₃: There is no significant statistical different between urban and rural parents in the negligence of the education of the girl child.
- HO₄: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of parents of high and low socio-economic status in the negligence of the education of the girl child.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey design in which the opinion of parents about the education of the girl child was sought through the use of questionnaire. The population of the study comprised all parents in Delta South Senatorial District. The parents comprised of varied background according to their gender, educational status, socio-economic status and location.

The instrument used for the study was the questionnaires tagged “parental attitude to girl child education scale” (PAGES). The instrument contained part ‘A’, which sought the demographic data of the respondents such as gender, educational background, location, socio-economic and work background. Part ‘B’ contains 20 items which are statement pertaining to the importance of the girl child education in a family and society to which respondents are to agree or disagree on a range of four-point scale. A mean score of 2.50 and above would indicate high value placed on the education of the girl child and hence willingness to send her to school whereas a mean score below 2.50 would mean negligence on the part of parents to educate the girl child and so would not send her to school.

The psychometric properties of the instrument for the study were determined by showing the instrument to lecturers in the department of Guidance and Counselling who confirmed the instrument for face validity. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha. The r computed was $r=0.79$ which is an index of high reliability and adequacy. Data collected were organized and analyzed. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and the t-test was computed and used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of female and male parents in the negligence of the education of the girl child.

Table 1: Analysis of negligence of girl child education based on gender of parents

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
Male	104	17.22	3.03				
Female	76	17.10	3.28	178	0.25	0.81	No Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

The result of table 1 indicates that there is no significant difference in the negligence of girl child education between male parents (M= 17.22, SD=3.03) and female parents (M=17.10, SD=3.28), $t(178) = 0.81, P > 0.05$). This means that gender of parents does not influence the negligence of the education of the girl child.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of educated and non-education parents in the negligence of the education of the girl child.

Table 2: Analysis of negligence of girl child education based on illiteracy level of parents

Illiteracy Level	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
Educated	114	17.45	3.34				
Non-Educated	66	16.69	2.68	178	1.65	0.12	No Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

The result of Table 2 shows that there is no significant difference in the negligence of girl child education between educated parents (M=17.45, SD =3.34) and non-educated parents (M=16.69, SD=2.68), $t(178)= 1.65, P > 0.05$. This means that illiteracy level of parents does not influence the negligence of the education of the girl child.

HO3: There is no significant statistical different between urban and rural parents in the negligence of the education of the girl child.

Table 3: Analysis of negligence of girl child education based on location of parents

Location	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
Urban	80	17.23	3.53				
Rural	100	17.13	2.78	178	0.19	0.84	No Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

The result of Table 3 revealed that there is no significant difference in the negligence of girl child education between parents living in rural areas (M=17.23, SD=3.53) and urban areas (M=17.13, SD=2.78), $t(178) =0.84, P > 0.05$. This means that location of parents does not influence the negligence of the education of the girl child.

HO4: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of parents of high and low socio-economic status in the negligence of the education of the girl child.

Table 4: Analysis of negligence of girl child education based on socio-economics status of parents

Socio-Economics Status	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
High	107	17.19	3.39				
Low	73	17.15	2.71	178	0.08	0.94	No Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

The result of Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference in the negligence of girl education between parents of high socio-economic status M=17.19, SD=3.39) and low socio-economic status (M=17.15, SD=2.71), $t(178)= 0.94, P > 0.05$). This means that socio-economic status of parents does not influence the negligence of the education of the girl child.

Discussion of Findings

It is clear from the result of the study that parents irrespective of gender, literacy, location and socio-economic status are disposed to the education of their girl child. This is not surprising because of the high rate of awareness and the campaign presently going on not to discriminate against the girl child in areas of politics, business, industry, education, jobs, and professions. It is important to note that Delta State is one of the educationally advantage states in Nigeria. In recent times, there has been awareness campaign in Delta State by beauty pageants and other women organizations under the umbrella of non-governmental organizations for parents to place economic and educational value on their girl child (DRTV News 6th Nov, 2015). This awareness in Delta State is likely to have contributed to why there is no significant difference in parents’ attitude to education of the girl child. The researcher

has also noted that schools in urban and rural areas of the state have very high percentage of female enrolment. (Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Asaba).

Most reports regarding the education of the girl child in Nigeria have always talked about gender disparity in which the females are painted to have been neglected (Bukar, 2011; World Bank, 2008): This is against the findings of this study. A plausible reason for this paradigm shift is the role played by information technology which has created awareness among both urban and rural dwellers, literate and non-literate, mothers and fathers, as well as rich and poor parents. Of course, it can be said that there are no longer villages as a result of migrations and interactions. Again, the poor, the uneducated parents i.e. mothers and fathers in the rural areas desire that their children especially the girl child should be educated in order to benefit from the opportunities available in the modern world. No doubt, the campaigns for women emancipation and the present dispensation where women have held important positions both in government, politics, education, industry, military etc in Nigeria have further increased this level of awareness that education is the way to bridge the gap between educated and non-educated, the rich and the poor as well as urban rural dwellers (Offorma, 2009).

Finally, the development strides in Delta State in which there are access roads and means of transportation to every part of the state, poverty alleviation and economic empowerment programme as well as free education for all pupils in basic and secondary schools would have also contributed to reason why there seems to be no negligence of the girl child education by parents in Delta State.

Counselling Implications

The study has revealed the beauty of education, information, awareness, and development in the attitude of people towards responsibility and avoidance of forms of malpractice in the family especially in the area of negligence of parental responsibilities to the child particularly the girl child. In the regard, counselling should be taken as an intervention for providing information for behaviour change. The following information can be provided to parents regarding the value of the girl child and need for the girl child education:

- A girl child is a member of the family who should be trained and be able to contribute to family growth.
- A girl child is a human being just like others and should be educated so that she would be able to fend herself.
- The girl child is a would-be mother who needs education to be able to survive, rear, guide and provide for her children.
- The girl child is a would-be wife who should be educated to be able to support her husband and family.
- The girl child has equal right as the male to education as enshrined in National Policy of Education for Nigeria, therefore, neglecting the education of the girl child is tantamount to malpractice on part of parents.

Conclusion

It could be concluded that parents in Delta State are willing to meet up with their responsibilities of bringing up and educating their girl child irrespective of their dwelling places, level of education, gender, and socio-economic status in a 21st century modern world. Counselling plays a vital role as an intervention in educating and informing parents about the value of the girl child education in the family.

Recommendations

The following can be recommended to avoid parental negligence of the role to be played by parents in educating the girl child:

1. Intensify campaigns to create awareness to the door steps of every parent in Delta State and indeed in Nigeria regarding the importance of educating the girl child and the value of the girl child and the value of the girl child in self development and contribution to family and national growth.
2. Campaigns of awareness should not be discriminatory but should be inclusive of all the characteristics of parents regarding their gender, literacy, location and socio-economic background.

References

- Ada, N. A. (1992). The paradox of equality opportunities for all citizens in Nigeria and the challenges of rural transformation in 1990. *Artscope Journal of the Arts and Hummanties* 2, 48–56.
- Ada, N. A. (2007). *Gender, power and politics in Nigeria communities*. Makardi: Aboki Publishers.
- Bukar, U. (2011) *Education of the girl child*. Nigeria communities. Blogsport.com/2011/03/education of the girl child htm/?m=1
- DRTV News the Nov. (2015). *Developmental Strides of Delta State Government and the role Beauty pageants in Tourism and Girl Child Education*.
- Enejere, E. (1991). ‘Woman and Political Education.’ In D. O. Ohizea & J. Njoku (Eds), *Nigeria woman and the challenges of our time*. Lagos: Malthouse Press Ltd. 44-51.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2006). *Basic and Senior Secondary Education Statistics in Nigeria 2004*. Abuja: Ministry of Education.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Policy on Education*. Abuja: Federal Government Press.
- Michael, I. (2011). *Emir Harps on Girl-Child Education Surviving on a shoestring Budget*. No 44, Nov. 3 p.32-34.
- Delta State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education (2015). *Statistics on Basic and Secondary School enrolment*. Asaba; Official Bulletin.
- Nwangwu, N. A. (1997). *UPE: Issues, Prospects and Problem*. Benin: Ethiope Publisher.
- Offorma, G. C. (2009). *Girl-Child Education in Africa*. Keynote address presented at the Conference for Federal University Woman of Africa Held in Lagos, Nigeria 16th -17th July, 2009.
- Okeke, E. A., Nzewi, U. M., & Njoku, Z. (2008). *Tracking School age Children Education Status in UNICEF, A field state*. Enugu: UNICEF p. 31.
- UN Charter and Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948). *Out of school primary female*. Accessed 1/11/15 at <http://www.tradingeconomics.com/nigeria/chain-wb-data-html>.
- Buchholz, K. (2022). *This is how much the global literacy rate grew over 200 years*. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/09/reading-writing-global-literacy-rate-changed>.
- World Bank (2008). *Education Indicator-Niger out of school primary female* <http://www.tradingeconomics.com/nigeria/chainweb-data-html>.
- World Conference on Education (1990). *out of school primary female*. <http://www.tradingeconomics.com/nigeria/chain-wb-data-html>.